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KERALA CALLING

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LET US STAY UNITED

The Monsoon usually falls on Kerala with a handkerchief to wipe out the tears of the humanity but this time it has taken a U- turn hitting hard on the cheeks of Kerala causing the State to whimper in fear. Shedding the inherent romantic spirit away, the Monsoon has become very coldhearted on the State. Nature is unpredictable and we, human beings, are very fragile. There is no 'awe' is flowing from the pens of writers this time but only scary stories of the floods.

The Monsoon wreaked unprecedented havoc and the entire state is on tenterhooks. Nevertheless, the State administration took precautionary measures and relief measures are underway. This is the time we stay united, casting aside differences in opinions, to extend our help to the affected. The Government appealed to the people to make generous contributions to the Chief Minister's Distress relief Fund to help those who have been affected. A toll free no 10 77 is instituted in all the Collectorates for this purpose.

State Level Coordination cell has opened at Secretariat under the leadership of Additional Chief Secretary P.H.Kurian and Operational round the clock in addition to the State Emergency Operations centre under Kerala State Disaster Management Authority. Necessary measures have been taken after coordinating with Army, Navy, Air Force, NDRF, Coast Guard and other Departments.

With cities and villages flooded in torrential waters, the State taking up the cudgels against a raging monsoon for the first time in our history. With the involvement of all, the Government is confident of overcoming the crisis. And, we have to. It is saddening that this tragedy occurs at the time of celebrating Onam and Bakrid. Citing the grave situation, the Government has resolved to call off the State sponsored Onam week celebrations and reroute the allocation to the Chief Minister's Distress Relief Fund.

This is the time we must stay united. We cannot be called human beings unless we exhibit our innate humaneness towards our brethren when they are earnestly seeking for our support.

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EDITORIAL MATERIALS

Articles/features appearing in this magazine are either commissioned or assigned. Nevertheless, other articles are also welcome. A maximum of 750 wordage is appreciated. Such items should be addressed to
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VIEWS

expressed in the articles published in Kerala Calling are not, necessarily, those of the government. Kerala Calling welcomes free expression of divergent views and exchange of ideas through its pages.

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THE UNABATED FURY OF THE MONSOON

6

The fury of the Monsoon is not yet over. The torrent has kept the State on tenterhooks and many have already been lost their houses and left with few belongings. Unfortunately, it claimed some precious lives as well.

In spite of the tense moments that loomed over the State, the Government acted on the dot by taking all precautionary measures during the crisis. And, it worked well. Red alert was declared prior to the shutter lifting of all major dams and people were shifted to safe zones. Rescue teams, including units of the Army, the Navy and the National Disaster Response Force (NDRF) worked hand in glove with the State administration and these efforts helped avert massive casualties. The Centre reached out to Kerala, offering a helping hand to tackle the situation. Union Minister for Home Affairs Rajnath Singh contacted Chief Minister Pinarayi Vijayan and assured the State of all possible help.

The Chief Minister, together with the cabinet ministers and the Leader of Opposition made aerial survey of the flood-hit areas. The State was able to get a central assistance of Rs 100. But, this is inadequate to reconstruct the damaged bridges and roads apart from extending help to those affected in the inundation. So, financial aid is solicited at this juncture of devastation.

The Government requests financial contribution to the Chief Minister's Distress Relief Fund so that everyone can play a pivotal role in the rebuilding of the lives of the flood affected people. A toll free no (1077) is in full swing in each district.

PAYMENT GATEWAY FOR REMITTING CONTRIBUTIONS

An online facility is instituted in order to remit financial assistance to Chief Minister's Distress Relief Fund (CMDRF). Through this, anyone can contribute donations in and out of the country. Using debit/credit cards or net banking, safe e-payment gateway is enabled through the website <https://donation.cmdrf.kerala.gov.in>. Receipt, given by Principal Secretary of the Finance Department on behalf of the State Government, will be available online right away. We request you to make use of this opportunity.

GOVERNMENT OF KERALA
Pinarayi Vijayan
CHIEF MINISTER

10.08.2018

Dear Friend,

Our State is in the midst of an unprecedented flood havoc. The calamity has caused immeasurable misery and devastation. Many lives were lost. Hundreds of homes were totally destroyed and many more were damaged in the rains. The water washed away many shops and commercial establishments. The roads in the State were damaged on a large scale, with some roads being completely devoured by the flood waters. Even bridges had collapsed. Crop losses occurred in most parts. The misery due to the rains has not ceased. We are not able to make a complete estimate of the losses as the water is still above the normal level in many places.

For the first time in history, 27 dams in the State had to be opened. Never before had the State witnessed a calamity of this scale. In spite of that, we responded to the crisis quickly. We were able to rescue the affected and relocate them to camps. The entire state machinery worked in unison to provide drinking water, food and clothes to people in these camps. The services of Central Forces and Disaster Response Forces were made available without any delay. Army, Navy, Air Force, NDRF and Coast Guard are presently engaged in an exemplary rescue effort. The Police, Fire Force and other officials of the State are also doing a model service. Elected representatives and volunteers actively took part in the relief efforts. The Ministers coordinated the relief efforts at the district level.

Now we have an important duty before us, the task of bringing life back to normalcy. The people of the State must come together for this effort. The leader of the opposition was also a part of the official team of Government that visited the affected areas. The situation demands from us a unity that would make us proud forever. The Union government has promised all possible assistance to the State.

We become civilized only when we show compassion towards those who are suffering. We came together during the time of Ockhi disaster. In a similar manner, we must realize that this is a calamity of the entire State. I urge all to consider this as a request of Kerala and contribute generously to relief efforts.

Yours sincerely,

Pinarayi Vijayan

Address to mail Cheque/Draft:

The Principal Secretary (Finance), Treasurer,
Chief Minister's Distress Relief Fund,
Secretariat, Thiruvananthapuram – 1.

Account details for transferring online:

Account Number: 67319948232
Bank: State Bank of India
Branch: City Branch, Thiruvananthapuram
IFS Code: SBIN0070028
PAN: AAAGD0584M
Name of Donee: CMDRF

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FESTIVAL ON DEMOCRACY

A Workshop For The Nation To Think And Act

10

Kerala has become a responsible role model for the country to think, act and progress in the social, economic and cultural spheres of India. And the cornerstone of Kerala's clarity in thinking, its ability to formulate path-breaking and defining policies, to create avenues of development and welfare with changing times; all stem from the quintessential 'Constitution of India'. The very essence and spirit of our Constitution is being literally followed in the State and expressed through one of our impactful democratic institutions – the Legislature. And the 'Festival on Democracy' is an earnest effort to explore and exhort in order to make our Constitutional bodies more powerful and to sustain the values of democracy in our country.

The two-day event had a befitting beginning when the Honorable President of India Ram Nath Kovind inaugurated the first conclave of the event on 6 August 2018. The enlivening and insightful speech of the honorable president was well received by the participants, which got reflected in the sessions that followed at different venues in the Kerala Legislative Assembly complex.

A galaxy of well-known personalities drawn from various spheres of public life attended the two-day event. Members of Parliament Varaprasad Rao, Majeed Memon, former member of the Lok Sabha Bhakta Charan Das, political thinkers like Prof Gopal Guru, Dr Kancha Ilaiah and P. S. Krishnan IAS (Rtd) were among the panel of eminent speakers, whose participation added value and purpose to 'Festival on Democracy'. Government of Kerala would roll out five more conclaves under this in the months ahead. This series of conclaves, organized as part of the concluding celebrations of the Kerala Legislative Assembly would leave a lasting impression in the minds of all those who cherish the ideals and values of democracy.

Kerala's DNA Continues to be Preserved:

President Ram Nath Kovind

Even in previous centuries, Kerala's social framework has encouraged debate and dialogue. This was the way of farsighted reformers such as Adi Sankaracharya, Sri Narayana Guru and Ayyankali, remarked President Ram Nath Kovind in his inaugural address at the 'Festival on Democracy' organized to mark the conclusion of the Diamond Jubilee celebrations of the Kerala Legislative Assembly.

In a lively and enlightening speech, the president of India said: "A person may believe in one faith or the other or he or she may not believe in any faith at all. That is not important. What matters most is the culture of educated and informed debate and of mutual accommodation that has been part of Kerala's DNA, which continues to be preserved. It must be preserved in public life and it must be preserved in this assembly."

Reflecting his thoughts on the different seminars on important themes of legislative democracy as part of the event, president Ram Nath Kovind said that all of those were extremely meaningful themes and that he was confident that the deliberations would translate into meaningful actions for the progress of legislative democracy in our country. Such a celebration of ideas was entirely in keeping with Kerala's rich intellectual legacy, the president observed.

Inviting the attention of the gathering, the president said: "Politics, public life and the quality of democracy are a reflection of the essential ethos of a society. As such, the Kerala assembly and its debates and discussions, the humanistic values that it has historically advocated and legislated on are a mirror to the traditions of this State. It was Kerala that gave our nation a towering personality in the form of President K. R. Narayanan, my distinguished predecessor in Rashtrapati Bhavan. He rose to the highest office from extremely challenging circumstances and did so with scholarship, hard work and determination."

President Ram Nath Kovind recalled the yeomen services and contributions of former chief ministers like E. M. S. Namboodiripad, R. Shankar and C. Achutha Menon in the formative years of the State. Their efforts were backed well by their successors like K. Karunakaran, E. K. Nayanar and the current chief minister Pinarayi Vijayan. The president described Justice V. R. Krishna Iyer a member of the first assembly as a cherished and much loved person and K. R. Gowri Amma as the most respected women politicians of independent India.

Further in his speech, president Ram Nath Kovind shared his thoughts on some of the landmark initiatives of the Kerala Legislative Assembly. He said: "From land reforms to panchayati raj, from literacy to healthcare, the people of Kerala have achieved a lot. This process has been aided by laws shaped and finalised in this House. It has led to social sector accomplishments that have come to be termed the 'Kerala Model'. The next stage of the 'Kerala model' should be to ensure greater opportunities for the youth of Kerala in their home State itself. For this, the gap in the incubation of entrepreneurial and business capacities in Kerala itself needs to be addressed by all stakeholders," the president added.

Sharing a concern, the president said that as he had already emphasised, the history of debate, mutual dignity and respect for another's point of view has been a hallmark of Kerala society. It had made Malayalis among the thought leaders of our country. These attributes had also influenced the civil and learned conduct of this House over the past 60 years. Debate, dissent and disagreement were perfectly acceptable and should be welcomed in our polity. But violence has no place in our Constitution. It would be appropriate if we could give some thought to this at the 'Festival of Democracy'.

President Ramnath Kovind concluded his address by greeting the people of Kerala in view of the upcoming Onam festival and he hoped that the festival would bring joy and prosperity to every family and every home in Kerala.

A LANDMARK IN THE ILLUSTRIOUS HISTORY OF KERALA LEGISLATIVE ASSEMBLY: Governor

“**T**his event is yet another landmark in the illustrious history of the Kerala Legislative Assembly, which continues to empower the marginalized sections of the society by acquainting them with the true spirit of democracy,” Governor Justice (Rtd) P. Sathasivam said while addressing the inaugural session of the ‘Festival on Democracy’ at the Legislature complex. Like the Parliament, the legislature too is akin to a university, where each member has to be like students, diligent in preparation and presentation. The task of each legislator is to rise up to the expectations of the society through systematic work, especially in matters of development, the Governor added.

Despite the fact that the legislators address the concerns of the society, people often lament the fall in the standards of democratic institutions and more importantly in the growing disregard for procedure and convention in such bodies, the governor opined.

“It may be true that newer issues need to be confronted through novel modes of protest and dissent. But, such protests cannot ignore the basic dignity of the democratic institution nor can they hamper the constitutional rights of the Members; no matter whether they rule or sit in the opposition,” the governor said.

According to the governor, the greatest celebration of democracy is when every ordinary citizen respects democratic values and cultural diversity, stands up for one’s legitimate rights and does not succumb to sectarian or communal thoughts. “Our task is to empower people to rise to such levels of thought and action, so that we can truly celebrate our democracy”, he said.

The Governor hoped that the sessions of the event with its focus on democratic empowerment of weaker sections, women, youth and the media would convey a strong message on the high standards that we intend to bring into our democracy. “Let us utilize this opportunity to create a Kerala model in strengthening democracy,” he said.

KERALA: THE TREND SETTER IN INDIAN DEMOCRACY:

Pinarayi Vijayan, Chief Minister

The introduction of a subject committee, examining proposed bills, had its inception in the Kerala Assembly and this practice had been later on adopted by other state Assemblies besides the Parliament. Thus, Kerala, which made seminal contributions to the democratic process in our country, became a trend-setter in infusing democratic values. Chief Minister Pinarayi Vijayan praised Kerala's contributions in uplifting democracy while delivering his speech in the inaugural session of Festival on Democracy at the Legislature Complex. In continuation with the already laid paragons on democracy,

the current LDF Government is making ground making interventions in the State.

The Chief Minister highlighted a few examples of these interventions. Kerala has retained the plan process, the SCP and TSP at a time when the Central Government dropped the plan process. These are essential in ensuring the most disadvantaged that there is a reasonable allocation of resources for them. Through targeted schemes and programmes, special attention is given to their specific needs. The State has allocated resources for the SCs and STs, which is more than their normative share. In this respect also,

Kerala is unrivalled. This allocation is proportional to population, lays Kerala on top against other states, as well as higher than that of any other state. The special recruitment drive is another bold step which ensures the adequate representation of the SCs and STs in government service.

Another milestone in bringing about social parity, priests belongs to backward and scheduled communities were appointed in temples under the Dewaswom Board. Thus, democracy becomes a tool for realizing equality and justice.

Secularism is the foundation of Indian

democracy. They are complementary to each other. And, when democracy vanishes, freedom follows the suit. The founding fathers of the Indian Republic had a clear idea of what we ought to be as a nascent and modern nation. They left no room for doubt regarding this when they enshrined it in the preamble of our Constitution. When the pillars of constitution, socialism and secularism are under threat, it is our duty to embrace those values stronger than ever before. 'The death of these values will spell the death of India'. The chief Minister reminded the people on safeguarding

the constitution of India.

India has a tradition of assimilating different schools of thought, languages and cultures. 'Unity in Diversity', our cherished ideal, makes the Indian democracy flourish. The chief minister reflected upon the great tradition of India.

It is high time we ought to examine the impact of 'post truth' politics on the democratic system. With the advent of social media, rumors are in the air for creating hatred and animosity. It is pathetic that, we, who ought to develop a scientific temper and a

spirit of inquiry, fall victims to these devious designs. These orchestrated campaigns try to weaken our democratic set up.

The Chief Minister reminded all who have assumed office after having sworn allegiance to the Indian constitution that it is their duty to protect democracy and strengthen secularism. Freedom can prevail only then. 'The Festival on Democracy would awaken a sense of guardianship among us with regard to safeguarding our constitution and democracy', he hoped.

DEMOCRACY withstands the test of time:

Ramesh Chennithala, Opposition Leader

“In spite of its inherent drawbacks, the democratic system has stood the test of time”. Opposition leader Ramesh Chennithala commented on while addressing the inaugural session of the Festival on Democracy at the Legislature complex. “The people of this country breathe democracy and freedom. Any effort to thwart their freedom and establish autocratic rule from any quarters will be resisted tooth and nail. This is the very reason why we are considered as the most successful and the largest democracy in the World”. He reflected upon the traits of Indian democracy.

The Opposition Leader said that creative and vibrant legislative assembly and legislations had been one of the prime reasons for the State remaining at the top for the past several years. “Since its formation in 1957, we have passed more than 1600 legislations including the Land Reforms Act, Educations Act, Right to Service Act and The Wetland Paddy Field Act among others. Visionary legislators and leaders who have graced this assembly have contributed immense-

ly to the progress made by the State over the years”, he said.

“The fundamental democratic principles of Sovereignty, Socialist, Secular, Democratic, republic enshrined in the preamble of our constitution, have ensured equal rights to all people irrespective of their cast, religion, creed, language among others”. The Opposition leader said.

“There is no doubt that democracy needs to be celebrated, but the actual spirit of democracy can be realized only when benefits of democracy reaches the oppressed and the underprivileged sections of the society. The true celebration of democracy happens when the lives of the downtrodden, the marginalized, and the underprivileged are bettered through creative legislations” he said.

The opposition leader concluded his speech by urging everyone to make sure that our great democracy would not be blemished by divisive forces. “I urge all the political parties, media and judiciary to stand united to resist any effort to stain our great constitution”. He concluded.

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President Ram Nath Kovind plants a sapling at the legislature complex

KERALA IS COMMITTED TO THE WELFARE OF THE MARGINALISED:

AK Balan, Minister for SC/ST

“**T**he marginalized and the backward sections in the society confronts various problems despite the fact that numerous laws in favour of them existing in the country” said Minister for SC/ST A.K. Balan on the inaugural session of Festival on Democracy. “The Constitution ensures them many rights. This is high time for all those concerned to protect these rights. The State Government is implementing many projects for the welfare of the marginalized and the backward sections. These projects are aimed at their overall development and ensuring job opportunities. Kerala has a long tradition of implementing many legislations and policies for the upliftment of these sections. There are many examples for these including the Land Reforms Act. The Land Reforms Act emancipated the weaker sections from the exploitation of feudal lords. The Festival on Democracy conducts many a debate on the various issues confronted by the marginalized and backward sections so that it will give a new direction for the activities for the upliftment of these sections” the minister said.

RESERVATION ESSENTIAL FOR ELIMINATING INEQUALITY: Varaprasad Rao

“In order to eliminate inequality and do justice to the backward sections, reservation is essential” said Thirupati M.P Varaprasad Rao. “Only 1% of the population does enjoy the 63% of the wealth and progress of the country. 80% of the backward sections are landless. The efforts made by each and every government to tackle these problems are inadequate”, he pointed out.

LAWS SHOULD BE IMPLEMENTED EFFECTIVELY

The lack of will power in implementing laws are the prime reason for the surging up of atrocities against the scheduled caste and scheduled tribes”, said the legislators participated in the Regional Conference on the theme of “Experiences and Possibilities of Judicial Interventions”. “The Constitution promises the marginalised protec-

tion and benefits. But, governments are not able to dispense these among them in the true sense. The function of the Governments has become on the basis of judicial verdict or the governments are scared of judicial intervention”, opined Minister for Forest and Wildlife K. Raju. “There are circumstances in which the culprits who do atrocities against the marginalised go unpunished. This will force us

to say that the judiciary also comes under the purview of criticism', said Gopakumar MLA. "Only 25.5% culprits are punished in India for committing crimes against the backward sections. In Kerala, it comes around 7.9% and this situation must be changed", said P.S. Krishnan IAS(Rtd), former Advisor of Government of Andhra. "The Judiciary system must be used effectively by the backward sections and the organisations can help them in this matter" he added.

The participants wanted to have separate courts in all districts for considering these cases. Reservation must be made mandatory in aided schools. The backward sections must be given rights on their lands. Many policemen have the prejudice that the scheduled castes and scheduled tribes have a criminal background. It must be changed. For this, many participants sought immediate measures.

KERALA MODEL DEVELOPMENT GAINING POPULARITY IN THE COUNTRY: KANCHA ILAIAH

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Taking part in the deliberations on 'Casteism and Uprising of Scheduled Communities' in the plenary session on day one of the 'Festival on Democracy' held at Kerala Legislative Assembly, the director of the Centre for Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, Dr Kancha Ilaiah said: "There is absolutely no doubt that the 'Kerala Model' of development is better than the much touted model of Gujarat." The Kerala model of SC / ST development is a real challenge for the Union government. It was from Kerala that the nation had the first dalit president and the first dalit chief justice of India in the form of K R Narayanan and K G Balakrishnan.

Further in his speech Dr Kancha Ilaiah pointed out that Kerala had made significant and powerful strides in changing the profile of dalits. There is a need for the comparative study of the health, educational and financial indicators of Kerala dalits with that

Eliminate educational gap for empowerment: P. S. Krishnan

of their brethren in Gujarat. One can easily identify visible changes in the lives of dalits in Kerala.

Dr Kancha observed that the SC/STs of Kerala demands for the redistribution of land and calls for the improvements in their housing conditions. It would be interesting to find out how the government of Kerala would address these demands and other development initiatives would further improve the lives of SC/STs in the State. He also suggested that English medium education with scholarship schemes would make SC/STs of Kerala equally competent like other communities in the State. Since the government is providing better salary in government schools, the standard of coaching should go higher than the schools in the private sector, he added.

Addressing the session on 'Concept of Empowerment' with particular reference to scheduled caste and scheduled tribes, P. S. Krishnan IAS pointed out that the term empowerment is often used loosely and rhetorically. It is necessary to be clear on what empowerment meant and what specific measures can secure empowerment of the powerless and disempowered classes.

Further in his address P. S. Krishnan said: "The methodology of oppression, exploitation and deprivation of scheduled tribes were different from that of scheduled castes. But the end result remains the same."

P S Krishnan said that various measures had been taken for the advancement of scheduled caste / tribes in the

seven decades of our Independent and Constitutional existence, they were not sufficient enough. Some of the measures required for SCs and STs are common but certain others have to be designed for addressing specific situations.

According to P. S. Krishnan, elimination of educational gap is an important measure for creating conditions that can bring about empowerment. The widespread network of anganwadis provide a potent platform for introducing quality pre-school education for children of SCs and STs. For this to happen, P. S. Krishnan observed that teachers should be trained in Montessori and other similar methods. This would provide scope for SCs, STs and other socially and educationally deprived communities a gainful employment, he added.

ADDRESS FAILURES IN SOCIAL JUSTICE

Prof. Gopal Guru

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Justice to members of the scheduled caste / tribe communities is possible through the emergence of a more powerful judiciary in this country, said Prof. Gopal Guru, Editor of Economic and Political Weekly (EPW). Addressing the session on 'Constitutional Justice: Reality and Hope' at the 'Festival on Democracy' Prof. Gopal said: "Present day laws and interventions of the judiciary have repeatedly failed the aspirations of the marginalized community. If that is the case, then there is a drastic need to dismantle the very concepts of the prevailing judicial system. If the scenario persists, then it will erode the spirit of justice in our country."

Further in his address, Prof Gopal said that in a country when governance fail and inefficiency creeps in, ensuring of social justice would invariably remain at the receiving end. But, if the situation was the opposite and if someone points out a failure in ensuring social justice, then that administration has the responsibility to take

the required correctional measures without any delay. In our country the students belonging to the backward class are getting deprived off the chances to pursue higher education. Gross irresponsibility on the part of the administrators have led to redirecting and spending of financial assistance, which was originally meant for the dalits and tribes. The situation exposes the inability of our judiciary to prevent such activities. Misuse of caste certificate is rampant and no effective counter measures had been taken, Prof. Gopal Guru opined.

"Our society is yet to learn and express mutual respect and decency. Caste based dominance has literally blocked the growth of moral fairness of the society. It is because of the existence of Constitutional bodies that continues to instill the hope of justice as envisioned in the Constitution. It is high time for these Constitutional bodies to ensure active involvement to ensure social, economic and educational rights to all citizens of this country.

LEGISLATIONS THAT POWERED THE KERALA MODEL

The Kerala Legislative Assembly had passed many landmark legislations, making Kerala a role model in the country. Some of these legislations opened up new avenues of growth to the scheduled caste/tribe communities in the State. Starting from the State formation in 1957 through to its diamond jubilee year, the State Assembly witnessed key legislations that revitalized all segments of Kerala society.

The Education and Right to Service bills and the Land Reforms Act that enabled landless peasants to be masters of their own land became revolutionary ones in the annals of Kerala's socio-economic reforms.

The first government led by chief minister E M S Namboodiripad passed the Education Bill that envisaged the concept of 'education for all'. Following this, successive governments implemented several reforms in this sector. The present government's 'Education Mission' as part of Navakeralam Mission, is also aimed at enhancing the quality of educational institutions by improving the infrastructure. In the higher education sector, many Universities were formed following these legislations. Now, we have separate universities for Science and Health.

In fact, the first Legislative Assembly in the country that passed legislation for the welfare of labourers was that of

Kerala. In 1974, agriculture labourers were provided with their due share of labour rights, which later went on to ensure provident fund to labourers and establishment of welfare boards for head-load, motor, coir, Khadi, handloom, sewing, Abkari and other segments of labourers. The Legislative Assembly of Kerala passed four laws exclusively for protecting labourers in the cashew industry. As a matter of fact, the kind of advancements in social security and awareness had been an outcome of translating several Bills into Acts by the legislature. They include the Bonded Labour Act of 1975 that liberated the scheduled tribe community in the Malabar region and the laws in 1980 for ensuring development in slum areas. The commissions for backward communities (1993) and for women (1995) were an outcome of farsighted legislative activism.

Implementation of decentralized planning in Kerala had been a major initiative of the State legislature, which eventually resulted in the three-tier panchayat system. The recruitment of employees through the Public Service Commission (PSC), to a good extent addressed the issue of social and economic inequalities. This was made possible by providing jobs in government sector to all sections of people through reservation. It was in 1970 that the Kerala Legislative Assembly passed the all important on the formation and functioning of the PSC. Over the years, the PSC had been strengthened by the legislature through timely amendments to the laws dealing with this establishment.

CASTE BASED VIOLENCE

“MERE EXECUTION OF LAWS INSUFFICIENT”

Indian judiciary functions as an authoritative interpreter of the Constitution and Law says Dr. N. K. Jayakumar, former secretary Kerala Legislative Assembly, in the plenary session on the ‘Experience and Possibilities of Judicial interventions’ held as part of ‘Festival on Democracy’. “In the backdrop of the plight of dalit women facing oppression and discrimination, only a fraction of incidents are reported since many dalits do not register cases. The country is answerable for this human rights violation and it has failed to protect the dalits against marginalization and oppression.” Referring to the world conference on ‘Racism and Related Tolerance’ Dr Jayakumar said that though the conference lauded India’s progress in terms of

protection, it has also pointed out the dalit sufferings due to discrimination at the hands of upper caste members.

In the course of his speech Dr Jayakumar said that mere execution of laws is not sufficient to ensure justice in case of caste based violence and atrocities. He pointed out the prime role of judiciary in the case of caste discrimination and violence. “We have to examine the actual impact of the court and its decisions on the life of the poor and marginalized. Yes, the Supreme Court has been diligent in some cases. There is a need to position the dalits in equanimity with other communities. And for addressing the issues of injustice, Judiciary should become more inclusive and proactive,” he opined.

Nissan and Tech Mahindra takes space in Kerala to set up IT Center

Shortly after Japanese auto major Nissan Motor announced its Digital Hub in Thiruvananthapuram, Tech Mahindra has decided to set up an IT Center that will cater to its global clients. A Memorandum of Understanding was exchanged between NISSAN Motor Co.Ltd and Govt of Kerala for 'Nissan Digital Hub'. Chief Minister Pinarayi Vijayan said that the signing with Nissan is a gigantic step towards the vision to make Kerala a 100% digital state.

Nissan's digital hub will be a research and development facility shared by the Renault-Nissan-Mitsubishi Alliance, a Franco-Japanese strategic partnership. The hub will function as the nerve centre of the company's research in electric and automated vehicles. The State Government will allot 30 acres of land in the first phase and another 40 acres in the second phase. This is the fifth digital hub of Nissan coming

up in Trivandrum after Yokohama in Japan, China, Paris and Nashville in US.

Nissan picked Kerala to set up its digital innovation hub owing to multiple factors like - talent pool in IT and engineering; airport connectivity; cost effectiveness; quality of life, social amenities; lack of traffic problems; and also the positive feedback from the successful IT companies at Technopark.

The company will initially begin operations in 25,000 sq.ft space in Yamuna building in the Technopark Phase III campus as well as other Co-Developer space. The company shall also be taking up space in the IT building that is coming up in Technocity. Nissan's digital innovation hub will host a team of engineers and scientists, working to create innovations in automated and electronic vehicles space. The company will be initiating research and development work in Artificial

Tech Mahindra

Intelligence, Cognitive analytics, Machine learning and other Digital technologies. On setting up operations, the company is expected to generate 3000 direct and multi times indirect employment opportunities. This campus will be named as 'Nissan Knowledge City'.

"The Government's vision of creating a hub of emerging technologies at Trivandrum is turning out to be a reality through this Knowledge City. With Nissan's strategic engagement, we are confident that we will be able to rope in a host of IT companies also to our state" said Technopark CEO, Hrishikesh Nair.

Tech Mahindra Limited has expressed their interest for an immediate 200 seater IT SEZ facility for which Technopark has released the allotment letter for 10 the half floor space at Ganga Tower, Technopark Phase 3. The space is of 12,000 sq.ft. The office will start its operation in three months. In

the initial phase, 200 people will get employment and once the campus is completed, around 2,000 jobs will be created. The facility will be catering to a gamut of the company's global client.

With Tech Mahindra deciding to set up operations in Technopark, Kerala can now boast of the five IT majors of the country having their presence in the state including Tata Consultancy Service, Infosys, Wipro, Cognizant. UST Global, another IT major also has its operations in Kerala.

Being one of India's largest IT Parks, Technopark is one of world's greenest Technopolis as well. Technopark came into existence in 1990 at Thiruvananthapuram. Technopark companies employ more than 56000 IT professionals. Spread across 760 acres of land with 9.7 million sq.ft built up space (completed) and about 400 companies operational at present.

DEBOUCHMENT

Creating a milestone in Kerala history, first women's battalion of the Kerala police passed out at Police Academy, Ramavarpuram, Thrissur. The state witnessed the passing out parade of 44 women's Battalion with intense courage and determination. Rather than being stereotypical, the women battalion became the symbol of empowerment by holding an AK 47 in their hands, wearing specially designed black uniform. This batch had completed 9 months long training and passed out in flying colours by redefining the canon.

Intensive training was given in special fields such as disaster management, computer education, jungle training and in first aid. Apart from these, they were trained in the Kalari, Yoga, Karate and Swimming. Out of 578 members, 44 have undergone commando training, including anti-terror operations and weaponry under the agencies like NSG. They were introduced to the key concepts in crime investigation and case diary preparations. One of the unique features about the batch is that the battalion members were given proficient international level training under the leadership of experi-

enced women instructors. Kidnapping scenes and terror attacks were showcased as a part of the mock drill and the musketeers were brilliant enough to handle the terror attack with utmost fortitude and determination.

The women were selected for special training by considering their special interest. The Government has plans to increase the strength of women's representation in the Kerala police by ensuring equality and freedom. This prime new commando batch has written the examination and completed the training through e-learning. They have completed the modules i, ii and iii of "I Know Gender" from the e-learning campus of women training centre, UNO.

The state is enough proud about the women's battalion because this promising batch is excelled in various fields by bringing a paradigm shift by rejecting the notions of familiar tunes. The batch includes many graduates, post graduates and diploma holders. They have unearthed their talents and paved way to the future generations. This batch is not only a pride for our state, but they also envisage a new sense of freedom.

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OF A NEW ERA

Cochin International Airport Limited (CIAL) has been selected for the Champion of Earth Prize -2018, the highest Environmental Honour instituted by the United Nations. The much coveted honour has been bestowed on CIAL for its successful execution of one of the revolutionary ideas of using solar energy. This made Cochin Airport, a first in the world fully powered by it.

A communiqué signed by Erik Solheim, United Nations Global chief of the Environment and Executive Director, UNEP, sent to V.J.Kurian, Managing Director, CIAL stated that 'this is the United Nations highest environmental accolade and reflects your leadership in the use of sustainable energy'. The communiqué further adds "Previous Champion laureates range from world leaders to inspire scientists-all visionaries who drive the world closer to its aspiration of environmental sustainability and a life of dignity for all. As the world's first fully solar powered airport, you set an ambitious example, that we hope many others will follow. The award will be presented at a gala ceremony on the sidelines of the General Assembly in New York on 26th September 2018.

Earlier a UN team led by Erik Solheim had visited Cochin Airport to know about its solar initiatives and held discussions with authorities, including Chief Minister Pinarayi Vijayan who is also the Chairman of the company. During his visit Solheim had revealed to the media that the United Nations was intended to endorse Cochin airport officially as the world's first airport fully powered by solar energy. The UN established Champion of Earth award in 2005 to recognise outstanding environmental leaders from the public and private sectors, and from civil society. There are four categories;

wherein the CIAL was chosen for 'Action and Inspiration' which recognises individuals or organizations that have taken bold environmental action, and, in doing so, inspired others to follow in their footsteps. The awardees of 2017 included Michelle Bachelet, President of Republic of Chile, NASA's Goddard Space Flight Centre, World's largest bike sharing app Mobike and Chinese afforestation community Saihanba.

CIAL, the company which owns and operates Country's first airport built under Public Private Partnership mode became power neutral in 18th August 2015 with the commissioning of its 12 MWp solar power plant. It scaled up the installed capacity to 30 MWp by April 2018. V.J.Kurian, who pioneered the idea has said that the UN recognition would transcend CIAL's green ideas to a global audience. "We showed the world that big infrastructure projects like Airport can be put into operation fully using alternative energy sources. By September 2018, the solar capacity at CIAL will be increased to 40 MWp, with a power potential of 60 million units per annum and resulting in a cost saving of approximately Rs.40 Crore per annum to the Airport. This will also avoid CO2 emissions by more than 9 lakh metric tons over the next 25 years, which is equivalent to planting 90 lakh trees or not driving 2400 million miles" - Kurian added.

In order to ensure optimum land utilization CIAL has successfully implemented organic farming of vegetables in an area between solar panels. The airport stands at fourth in the country in terms of international traffic and seventh in total traffic that has handled ten million passengers in 2017-18.

UN HONOUR LANDS ON CIAL

A communiqué signed by Erik Solheim, United Nation’s Global chief of the Environment and Executive Director, UNEP, sent to V.J.Kurian, Managing Director, CIAL stated that ‘this is the United Nation’s highest environmental accolade and reflects your leadership in the use of sustainable energy ‘.

ASSURING A HAPPY ONAM

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*Consumerfed is all ready to meet the requirements to
celebrate a Happy Onam*

Onam is a festival of nostalgia for every Keralites. We celebrate each Onam in the memory of by-gone days which fostered the values of equality. By overcoming the harsh realities of everyday life, irrespective of caste and religion, by having 'sadya' and wearing new dress everyone tries to celebrate Onam in its true spirit. So much so that Onam is the festival of market as well. Intense price hike in the Onam market and the cheap produce are the main reasons for this. The Kerala Government takes position along with the destitute who tries hard to meet their needs. Consumerfed is one of the co operative institutions that helps the needy meet their needs. Consumerfed is opening 3500 festival markets to control the price hike in the Onam market.

In order to celebrate Onam for everyone, it is necessary to make available the high quality produce and products at a reasonable price. It is because of this reason the co operative sector has planned to open Onam market across the state. The products are available at the subsidy rate. Consumerfed ensures the control of price hiking with the effective intervention in the market.

3500 Onam markets works under the initiatives of Thrive-ni super market of Consumer Federation, primary cooperative societies, Neethi stores run by the cooperative societies, fisherman cooperative societies, women cooperative societies, SC ST cooperative societies, District consumer cooperative store, employees cooperative societies, agriculture cooperative societies and the consumer

societies. Selected items of 41 products which has discount ranging from 750 to 900 rupees will be available in the Onam market.

The resources for this have been already purchased in transparency via e tender and NCDX. Around 80% have been distributed completely from the go down. Consumerfed has taken measures to ensure the quality of the products. The scientists from the Central Government certified laboratory of Cashew Export Promotion Council were active from august 1st to collect the samples from the laboratory and the quality of the products is checked in their laboratory. We have to acknowledge the effort made by the Consumerfed to send back the products that has low quality.

The products such as payasam mix, maida, chilly powder, turmeric powder and salt will be available in the Onam

market. Other grocery products will be available in the Consumerfed go down with the price less than that of the MRP. The cooperative society can sell the items through the Onam market. The society is selected in such way that to avail the Onam market in the panchayaths, municipalities and corporations across the state. Consumerfed is availing concession for the festival Bakrid also.

By raising the slogan of 'Onam 2018 with Consumerfed', Consumerfed and co operation sector is ready to control the price hike and to ensure the availability good quality products. The Government is trying to safeguard the state to celebrate Onam without being pushed into the edges of price hiking. The Government assures to continue the activities to cease the price hike and to deliver good quality products with effective market intervention. The Government is executing projects in time bound manner to bring back Kerala's bygone days spirit and values.

ENSURING A BRIGHT FESTIVAL SEASON

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During the last month, Kerala witnessed an unprecedented rain havoc in the entire parts of the state. However the state Government rose to the occasion by taking all remedial measures by availing all its resources. The department of food and civil supplies has provided sufficient food article in the flood affected area in coordination with the department of revenue. Now the Onam and Bakrid season has started. The economic well being of a society depends on stability in prices in the open market. A vigorous Public distribution system, which intervenes in the market at the time of hike in prices, is indispensable for ensuring stability of price. In order to control the price hike and to distribute essential items to the public, Market intervention operations have been introduced in the state along with the normal rationing system. As the nodal agency of the Government to execute the market Intervention program in Kerala, Supplyco is effectively intervene the market by distributing essential items like rice, sugar, pulses and spices at the bare minimum prices, ie average 50% less than the open market prices.

All the measures taken by the corporation have been widely appreciated and became a role model to the entire country. The objective behind the incorporation of Civil

Supplies Corporation was Market Intervention to stabilize the price trend in the open market, especially during festival seasons. To get this objective fulfilled, the Kerala State Civil Supplies Corporation Ltd. has been conducting special fairs throughout Kerala as a part of market intervention scheme of the Government of Kerala with the main aim of arresting artificial price hike and exploitation of consumers by fraudulent traders during the festival seasons. The trade fairs conducting in Onam -Bakrid seasons are intended to make available the essential commodities to the reach of the common man at a price below the open market rates.

This year Thiruvonam falls on August 25. This year also, Supplyco conducts District/Taluk Onam fairs & markets in the State ensuring at least one fair/market in each Assembly constituency. Special Mini Fairs will be conducted in panchayaths where there are no Supplyco Outlets. In addition to the above, all Supplyco outlets will be functioning as Onam mini fairs during the peak days of Onam. The details of Onam fairs and markets conducted during 2018 are as follows.

Besides these fairs & markets, Special Onam Mini Fairs will be conducted for a period of 5 days from August 20 in Panchayaths where there are no Supplyco outlets. In addition,

SI No	Name of the Fairs	Total No of Fairs	Places	Duration
1	District Onam Fairs	14	In all District Headquarters	10/08/2018 to 24/08/2018 (15 days)
2	Taluk Onam Fairs	75	One Taluk Fair in each Taluk preferably in Taluk Headquarters	16/08/2018 to 24/08/2018 (09 days)
3	Onam Markets	78	Detached/Attached to Prominent Outlets in the areas as done last year ensuring at least one Onam Market/Fair in each Assembly constituency.	20/08/2018 to 24/08/2018 (05 days)

all Supplyco outlets will function as Onam Mini Fairs for a period of 5 days from August 20 .

MAJOR ACTIVITIES DURING ONAM

Ensuring availability of essential items in all outlets and fairs

In order to ensure availability of all the essential items in our outlets and special fairs, Supplyco has taken necessary

steps to purchase double the normal requirement of all the items. For this purpose, 2 e-tenders were floated last month and purchase orders were placed well in advance to ensure times supply. 315 Crores were spent for the purchase activity alone taking into account of the coming Onam season.

Mega Fiesta mode functioning of District Fairs

Supplyco’s ‘District Onam Fairs 2018’ have been arranged in

a grand fiesta mode. In all the District Fairs, we have ensured the participation of various Government agencies by opening their exclusive stalls. Major such stalls are HortiCorp, Milma, Kudumbasree, SAF, Vanasree, KEPCO, MPI, Coir Corporation, Hanveev etc. Food courts and payasams counters will also be arranged in the District Fairs. In Metro cities, children's play area will also be provided. The arrangements, such as shed construction, setting up of stalls, storage of goods, etc. are at the final stage.

SALES PROMOTION SCHEMES

To boost up the sales and to attract existing as well as new customers, it is planned to conduct three types of promotional schemes in the outlets and fairs during Onam season. The details of the proposed schemes are given

below.

Onam Sammanamazha 2018: This scheme covers all the Supplyco outlets. A gift coupon will be issued to the customers for the purchase of articles worth Rs 1,500/- in a single bill involving at least one Sabari item (except subsidized coconut oil). For every additional purchase of Rs 1000/-, additional coupon will be issued. Gold coins will be distributed to 6 winners through the lucky draw of coupons.

Assured Gift Scheme: This scheme is limited to District Onam fairs only and will be in effect during the period of functioning of the fair only. A customer who purchases items worth Rs 2000/- and above will be issued an assured gift.

Daily Gift Scheme: Daily lucky draws will be conducted in

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Supplyco is also carrying out distribution of 5 kg rice to school children and free kits to tribal families in the state as per the requests of Education and Scheduled Tribes Department respectively.

each detached fair and gifts worth a total of Rs 1000 will be given to the winners (2 persons).

Gift Coupons and Special Onam kits

To facilitate various employees working in Government and other PSUs, a KIT Gift Coupon has been designed this year.

In connection with Onam, Corporate offices in private and public sector will be providing various benefits to their employees. We are introducing a GIFT COUPON in the denominations of Rs.500, Rs.1000, Rs.2000 and Rs.2500 which can be redeemed at our outlets on production of the same. Since the benefits given to the employees are not misused or spent for unnecessary purpose, the employer may prefer the Supplyco GIFT coupon to their employees so that they purchase essential items for their households.

In addition to the above, it is planned to introduce a special Supplyco Onam Basket at an attractive discount rate. Provision items essentially needed during Onam days viz. rice (matta/jaya/kuruva), sugar, coconut oil, green gram dhal, ghee, lobia, Toordhal, mustard, methi, curry powders, masala powders, asafoetida etc. will be included in the kit. Maximum selling price of a kit is fixed at Rs 950.00. By purchasing the special Onam kit from Supplyco, a customer can enjoy the benefit of 20-30 % discount on FMCG items and subsidies of listed items on production of the ration card.

Distribution of free Onam kits to AAY families

This year also, Supplyco will distribute free Onam kits to the 5,95,800 AAY households in the state as per the order of the Government. The contents of the kit are rice, Green Gram, Bengal Gram and tea. An amount of Rs. 6.91 Crores will be spent for distributing free kits to entire AAY households.

Distribution of special sugar to entire cardholders

During 2018 Onam season, 1 kg (Onam special) sugar will be issued to entire ration cardholders in the state as per the orders received from the Government. Expected cost for this scheme is around Rs 16.17 Crores.

In addition to the above, Supplyco is also carrying out distribution of 5 kg rice to school children and free kits to tribal families in the state as per the requests of Education and Scheduled Tribes Department respectively. The Food grain Allocation to the Non-Priority sector (White card card holders) is also raised to 6 kg per card for the Onam festival season. We hope that the effort taken by the Government for the preparation of Onam will definitely benefit the people to have a better enjoyment in this season

MIRTH IN THE WATERS

The Malabar River Festival is South India's only extreme adventure competition organized on the behalf of Kerala Tourism by DTPC Kozhikode and Madras Fun Tools

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From the very beginning of his visit in Kerala, the photographer Nick Ut, renowned worldwide for taking the epoch-making image of the Napalm girl, longed to see an elephant parade. It was most unlikely for the organisers to fix a place since the month, March, heralds the end of the festival season in the State. It was not the high season. Nick fell in the grip of blues as nothing else could quench the thirst of famous Leica lenses but the array of elephants. On his whistle- stop travel by road across Kerala, he came to know that an elephant parade was about to begin at a nearby temple in the outskirts of Kollam district. Nick together with his friend Raul Roa of Los Angeles Times, lost no time. In excitement, they rushed to the spot leaving their lunch wait for them back in the hotel. Much to the horror of the organisers, Nick got lost in the crowd including foreigners. But, an hour after, they received the call from Nick which brought their smiles back. He was reclining in his bed back at the hotel after taking the rare pictures of the event. He was ebullient with joy at the spectacle of the 41 gloriously bedecked elephant parade which the renowned photographer witnessed for the first time in his life!

This is an excellent example of the changing trend among the tourists visiting Kerala. Yes, they like to watch rare events which are exclusive to each country and season. And, Kerala can be more than a visual treat to many of them if they are provided with rare events.

The Prospects of Event Tourism

Every event has some alluring element in it and event tourism is not an exception. It is getting faster and faster across the globe. Being an irresistible temptation, it beckons large volumes of tourists to the destinations where the events are conducted. Owing to its wide media coverage, international as well as domestic tourists have come to know about the events in our State. An excellent paragon is that of the Nehru Trophy Boat Race conducted every year at Punnamada back waters, Alappuzha.

According to Kerala planning board report (2017) shows that Kerala tourism will allocate more resources to develop destination and different activities with potential, including Biennale, different diverse festival and special events,

relatively unexplored tourist potentials in Kerala.

Malabar River Festival

The Malabar River Festival is South India's only extreme adventure competition organized on the behalf of Kerala Tourism by DTPC Kozhikode and Madras Fun Tools. Miraculous in nature, the Malabar River festival is conducted with the participation of athletes from around 25 countries. With over \$20,000 to be won in cash prizes, the Malabar River Festival is stepping up to become one of the biggest cash purse ever for a paddling event worldwide.

Every festival in Malabar is celebrated with much gaiety and stands out with people's participation and involvement. More attracted, doubtlessly, the youth and the children. The propaganda is carried over, mostly, by the social media. The event's online influence is astounding. It has an incredible online influence of 20 million worldwide. It is really worth watching the rhythm of Monsoon together with the rhapsodies of the race boats.

The River festival is categorised into Professional and Intermediate. Both have different sections like Trail, Down River and Boat cross. The stirring of oars and splashing of water in Boater Cross, a kind of whitewater kayaking, make one propel to the tip of his seat! Real dashing moments are assured.

The Malabar River festival brings out the charm and adventure of every event sport. Over 100 kayakers and rafters from 18 countries including USA, France, New Zealand, Australia, Germany, Spain, Scotland, Canada and Austria participate in the event. Kozhikode, the city of festivals brims with joy on these days.

The fame of Kozhikode is incomplete if the cuisine it provides will not be tasted on. Anyone, gifted with a discerning palate, finds the city tempting. However, it is hard mention a single item as the varieties are many. The people friendly ambience adds another feather in the cap of the city. Noted for the real party-giving nature of the people, you won't feel a stranger in the city any longer.

Every event has some alluring element in it and event tourism is not an exception. It is getting faster and faster across the globe. Being an irresistible temptation, it beckons large volumes of tourists to the destinations where the events are conducted.

Celebrating the sporting spirit of 45 nations, the 18th Asian Games is set to be held in Jakarta and Palembang in Indonesia. And, for the first time in history the Games is being held in two cities, two historic cities. It is Indonesia's second Asian Games after the fourth Games in 1962. Over two weeks of drama, excitement and passion are in the store.

India is one of the five founder members of the erstwhile Asian Games Federation, formed in 1949, the forerunner of the present Olympic Council of Asia. Further, we were the hosts for the inaugural edition in 1951 with New Delhi as the host city. Now the continental sports has gone from strength to strength, especially with China joining the competition. It has emerged as the second largest mega sports event behind the Olympics.

Jakarta was selected to host the present edition when Hanoi, Vietnam pulled out due to financial constraints. In less than a month Indonesia turned up and Olympic Council of Asia had not been left in the lurch for long. The 18th Games was originally scheduled to take place in 2019 to avoid the

clash with Commonwealth Games and even World Cup football and Winter Olympics. It has to be brought forward by a year since the presidential election in Indonesia was taking place in 2019.

Despite the historical role India played in starting the Games, our performance in the competition was not that good till date. In the last Games held in Incheon, South Korea we were 8th in the final medals tally with 11 gold, 10 silver and 36 bronze. But Kerala can feel proud as we have contributed much to India's medal kitty almost all the time. Kerala's contribution in track and field was superb.

Kosuka Hagino of Japan was adjudged the Most Valuable Player in 2014 as the recognition for the swimmer's hegemony in the pool. The 20 year old university student won 7 medals, including 4 golds. Had there been such an award in 1986 at Seoul, P T Usha would have won it. Usha won four gold and a silver there, the fourth was by anchoring the 4 x 400 m relay team to victory. She was beaten in 100 m by Lydia Divega, the Philippine beauty, a repeat of 1982. Usha's spectacular show in Seoul put India in good stead.

ENERGY OF ASIA 2018 Asian Games

18th ASIAN GAMES
**Jakarta
Palembang
2018**

Further, there had been no match to that excellent gold hunt as far as India is concerned .

T. C. Yohannan's super long jump in Teheran in 1974 also stands apart. With a jump of 8.07 meters Yohannan shattered the Asian Record as well. And it was intact till 1992 and the Games record till 1994. M.D. Valsamma eclipsed Asian record while winning 400 m hurdles gold in 1982 clocking 58.47 seconds.

Before taking up our prospects in the coming Asiad we must understand, in the inaugural edition two Malayalees , Tiruvalla Pappan and Kottiyam Saleh won gold being part of the football team.

And it was O. L Thomas who won the first medal as a Malayalee in track and field. He won a bronze in 1970 in the 4 x 100 m relay. Murali Kuttan and Merzy Kuttan became the first Keralite couple to have won Asiad medals. Murali won silver in relay and bronze in the 400 m where as Merzy won silver in the long jump in 1982.

And set for Jakarta , P. R Sreejesh leads the Indian hockey team. Being reigning champions, the responsibility is high. Sreejesh was the star when India beat Pakistan in shot out in the finals 4 years ago. Now ranked 5th India stands a good chance to be in the podium , maybe with the Gold for the 4th time overall.

In track Muhammad Anas reminds P. T Usha with entry in four events, 200m, 400m, 4x400m relay and mixed relay. He just missed the bronze in Gold Coast Commonwealth Games in one lap , but here stands a good chance.

Jinson Johnson competes in 800m and 1500m. Other than the Asian champion, of late, Johnson shattered the two lap national record created by legendary athlete Sreram Singh in 1976 Olympics. Of course , Johnson could bring laurels. P. U Chithra has a lot to tell with a medal. Let's wish the Asian champion the very best in one mile. SreeSankar in long jump with a life best of 7.99 m can go well to land a medal.

K. T Irfan, K. S Jeevan, Jithu Baby, Kunju Muhammmad, Rakesh

Babu, Tintu Luka, Anu Raghavan, Jisna Mathew, V. K Vismaya are all in the preliminary list. Some have to come out successful in the final trials. Same is the case with Neena and Nayana in long jump. For sure their life best if repeated can land both the ladies a medal it seems. In volleyball Minimal Abraham from Railways is the captain. And in the men's team three have represented Kerala.

In Kurash, P C Aswin (Police) and N. B Bineesha (Trichur) are expected to do well. In rowing and canoeing though Keralites had a good haul of medals, silver and bronze over the years, this time there is no one from Kerala to compete. But former medalists Saji Thomas , Siji Kumar along with Mujeeb Rehman are the coaches.

And, Sajjan Prakash is very much there to show our swimming potential. With Sandeep Sejwal winning bronze in the 50 m breaststroke in the last edition and is set to go far ahead this time, Sajjan has a role model. Sajjan the 2nd Malayalee Olympian swimmer after Sebastian Xavier has a long way to go but for sure, has the potential.

Yes, amongst all the mediocrity, there can be a few stellar individual performances from our stars, which can demolish the opponents with grace and skill.

As in women's volleyball and men's hockey Indian women's basketball team too has a Keralite captain. P.S. Jeena of KSEB will lead the side. Stephy Nixon and P.G. Anjana are the other Keralites in the squad. Further Priyanka Prabhakar who represents Karnataka is from Palakkad.

Jeena was in the 2014 Asian Games team also and then it was another Keralite Smrithi Radhakrishnan who led the team.

Sajjan Prakash will compete in three events. 100 m and 200 m butterfly and 200 m freestyle. Of late he won a gold, three silver and a bronze in Malaysian Open after having 2 months training in South Africa. Now he is back with coach Jayakumar.

AN ASCENT TO THE PAST

The relevance of folktales, myth and epics remain afresh amidst the sick hurry and palsied heart of modern man. They transcend the generations of people who passed on these stories and keep us connected to our traditions and indeed shape our culture. Here comes the combo delight of artistry, history, adventure, tourism, herbal garden, heli-taxi service, rejuvenation and what not in the maiden BOT (Build- Operation-Transfer) project in Kerala. The Jatayupara nature park, the state's first BOT- model ecotourism project at Chadayamangalam village in Kollam district of Kerala rechristened as Jatayu Earth's center is all set to lure the tourist map of India as well as the tourist influx of God's Own Country. The second phase of Jatayu Earth's Center will be inaugurated by Chief Minister Pinarayi Vijayan on 17th August, 2018. The 200 ft long, 150ft wide and 70ft tall sculpture is the largest functional bird sculpture in the world with an entry into the Guinness Book of World Records. It is a matter of immense pride and privilege for Kerala Tourism as this co-

lossal structure has carved a new phase as well as face for the charismatic land of greenery and scenery.

The project located at Chadayamangalam incorporates the Sculpture of the great mythical bird Jatayu mentioned in the Hindu epic Ramayana, cable car fully manufactured in Switzerland, adventure park and helicopter local flying service. Helicopter local flying service is offered for the very first time in the state as part of a tourism project. The first ultra-modern cable cars in south India, imported from Switzerland, will take visitors across an elevated distance of 500m- from the base station to the top- in five minutes. There will be 16 cable cars, each with a seating capacity of eight. Their glass body will ensure an enchanting view of the surrounding areas for the visitors. The most modern cable car facility manufactured in Switzerland is arranged to reach the statue and is launched for the first time in India. The journey in the cable car will be a spectacular experience cum visual pleasure for the tourists.

The largest bird sculpture in the world showcases amenities of international standards, entertainment programmes and artistic performances with an emphasis on culture tourism leaves no stone unturned to evolve as a milestone in the tourism development of Kerala. Jatayu Earth's Center is the debut joint effort by the Tourism Department of Kerala and Mr. Rajiv Anchal along with private equity holders to create a destination, which is a unique combination of all aspects of tourism and offers a complete Kerala, God's Own Country experience to every concept. The concept is the brain child of renowned film director, art director and sculptor Mr. Rajiv Anchal, and his team took ten years to meticulously design and complete this monumental project. Guruchandrika Builders and Property Pvt. Ltd. have leased the government owned land for 30 years to build and operate Jatayu Earth's Center.

The giant bird sculpture clinched a place in the Guinness Book of World Records as the largest functional bird sculpture in the world is a harmonious blend of imagination and creativity. Rajiv Anchal, the master brain of this marvel believes in the inclusive development of humanity through creative artistic excellence. Kerala Tourism will promote the Jatayu Earth's Center as its new product by branding it as 'international tourism cultural center'. It would be marketed by Kerala Tourism as its new tourism product in international fairs and festivals.

In a place replete with hills, valleys, caves and vegetation, this monumental project with a huge sculpture of the mythical bird in Ramayana is an outstanding replica of sustainable and eco-friendly tourism in India. Spread over 65 acres across four hills, Jatayu center does not just include adventure sports and camping experiences, but also a healing center that practices the traditional practice of Siddha medicine. One can partake in electrifying activities such as hill camping, trekking, bouldering, rappelling, zip lining, rock climbing, archery and shooting.

The adventure field in the park will have several options for activities like paint ball, laser tag, archery, rifle shooting, rock climbing and bouldering. It will also house ayurvedic cave resorts. The centre has imported 16 cable cars from Switzerland at a cost of Rs. 40 crore to provide the visitors a mind blowing view of the Jatayupara by travelling uphill and downhill. The ropeway is installed and operated by Usha Breco Limited. A sum of Rs.2500 will be charged for the package in the adventure park that includes adventure segments and food. An audio-visual museum is built inside the sculpture which spans over five levels. The virtual reality museum inside the sculpture is designed to promote the idea of harmony. A Rama temple and its mythical markings are in a fenced area on the hill top, which is managed by a private trust. A rain water reservoir is made on the hill top with a capacity to hold 1.5 million litres of water. Art performanc-

es would also be performed near the sculpture to present the place as a cultural hub. The hamlet of Chadayamangalam, along MC Road, and the heritage site of Jatayupara would thus be a blend of culture of the state and a tourism spot. The museum and 6D theatre inside the bird will be materialized soon. The park sprawls over 65 acres of land and is home to a giant sculpture of Jatayu.

In the great epic of Ramayana, Jatayu is epitomized as a noble bird of divine genesis. One day, he happened to hear the wistful cry of a lady. It was Sita lamenting for help while she was being abducted to Lanka by the demon king Ravana. Although Jatayu rushed to her rescue by stopping Ravana's chariot namely Pushpaka Vimana and engaged in a battle with him, all the efforts were in vain. Ravana took his powerful sword Chandrhasa, cut off the bird's left wing and went away with Sita. Believed to be the place where the mythical creature, Jatayu had fallen after being mortally wounded by Ravana before he fled to Lanka with Sita, the mighty rock of Jatayupara in the town of Chadayamangalam, near Kollam, has been fascinating travelers and pilgrims since time immemorial. Two years ago, Jatayupara was back in the lime-light with the announcement of a sustainable tourist and adventure centre to be underway. The anthropological concepts of 'little tradition' and 'great tradition' deserve mention here. It may be assumed that all civilizations start from a primary or orthogenetic level of cultural organizations. As time passes, they are diversified through two processes that are, internal growth and external contact. What is more

significant is cultural contact with outside or other cultures. McKim Marriott says that in the structure of the village culture and its social organization elements of both the little tradition and great tradition are found. He found that there is constant interaction between little tradition and great tradition and this in turn helps in cultural continuity in the face of modernization, westernization etc. Little tradition comprises local customs, rites, rituals, dialects and Great tradition incorporates legitimate form of all these things. The folks and peasantry follow the 'little tradition' of village where as the second division of elites follow the great tradition. This consists of the tradition contained in epics, puranas etc. When the elements of little tradition move upward, Marriott calls it as 'universalization'.

The practice of great tradition and little traditions foster collaboration, cooperation and unequal interaction between the two. Custom is what people follow and do collectively and transmit the same from one generation to another. Through the regularity of interaction between the two, the Indian civilization marches forward. In a civilization, there is a great tradition of the reflective few, and there is a little tradition of largely unreflective many. The versions of Ramayana and Mahabharata form the basis of cultural performances. These two great epics have their local versions which have been written in simpler languages with local example for local folk. The two traditions are interdependent. Great and little tradition have long affected each other and continued to do so. Great epics have arisen out of elements of tradi-

tional tale-telling by many people, and epics have returned again to the peasantry for modification and incorporation into local culture. Great and little tradition can be thought of as two currents of thought and action, distinguishable, yet ever flowing into and out of each other.

Jatayu Earth's Center exemplifies the inextricable interlacing of local practices and historical significance. The 'little tradition' Jatayupara (Jatayu rock) from a local village of Kollam district in Kerala is elevated to the status of the 'great tradition' of Pan Indian Ramayana's immortal characters. It adds to the glory and God somewhere near somewhere far. There is a pond near the rock which is said to be formed by the stroke of Jatayu's beak. It has water throughout the year and never goes dry. Legends also hint that Lord Rama later came to Jatayupara and gave moksha to the wounded and dying Jatayu. The good bird told narrated the entire story and hence, Rama got the vital information about his better half. There is the mark of a foot print said to be that of the Lord. A temple dedicated to him can be experienced in an adjacent compound.

Sky cycling, campfire, live kitchen, live music, moon light dinner for family with live music and a herbal garden with wide variety of plants beckons nature lovers with an opportunity to be part of preservation and protection

of natural eco system. A Ten- day long Siddha rejuvenation package and traditional Siddha rejuvenation in natural caves with accommodation facilities manifest the healing impact Lord Rama had on knowing about his abducted wife. The natural caves are all set to lavish the warmth and soothing effect for crushed and broken souls to move ahead despite all the problems and prospects in the general absurdity of life. With photographs of a gigantic concrete sculpture of Jatayu in construction being circulated on social media and mainstream media, an optimistic exodus is yearning to have a glimpse of this promising cultural hub. The nature park has been started with the aim of promoting mythology, adventure and wellness tourism.

Jatayu died protecting a woman's honour and that is what the sculpture stands for. According to Rajiv Anchal, it also represents a bygone era when humans, birds, animals and other living forms cared for each other as fellow beings and lived peacefully on this mighty planet of Earth. The sculpture of the giant bird sitting on top of a hill is beginning to spread its wings to rescue and save the honour of many Sitas in this contemporary world where rape, prostitution are in our active vocabulary and crime rate against women are rampant. Jatayu bestows a note of optimism as 'men may come and men may go but he goes on forever'. Jatayu Earth's Center glimmers hope and allures humanity 'for a life of sensations rather than of thoughts'.

E.P.Jayarajan swearing in as Minister at Raj Bhavan

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▶ Chief Minister Pinarayi Vijayan congratulating E.P.Jayarajan, who was sworn in as Minister, at Raj Bhavan. Governor P.Sathasivam is seen

Nascom Data Security Council Award for the excellence in cyber investigations

1

State with special department for women welfare and Gender budgeting

2

First in 10 criteria including background facilities, social safety, human resource

3

State with highest minimum wages in the nation

4

Only state in India free from communal riots as per the study of National Crime Records Bureau

5

First state to come up with 'Sexual Assault Forensic Evidence' (SAFE) kit for collecting evidence against sexual assault in a scientific manner

6

First state with proper sanitation facilities among the densely populated states

7

First state to allot budget in the proportion of population among Scheduled Caste and Tribes and Tribal community

8

'Vayojanshretta' award for Kerala's 'Vayomithram' Project

9

Cop today International Police excellence award for Janamaithri Police System

10

IndiaToday award for maintaining the best Law and Order

11

First state in the New Delhi Public Affairs Centre index

12

First state to declare internet facility as the Right of Citizen

13

No.

14

Only state with complete electrification

15

First state to declare transgender policy. Highest health-life index

16

State with least corruption - accreditation of centre for media studies

17

Model Student Police scheme

18

Modern roads in villages

19

International Standard free education

20

Free availability of health treatment

Changes are Evident Forward We March

NAAM MUNNOTTU
Chief Minister's Weekly
Interactive Television Programme

Sunday 7.30 PM Doordarshan, Asianet News, Mathrubhumi, Reporter
Sunday 8 PM News 18 Kerala **Monday 7.30 PM** Media One **10 PM** Doordarshan (Repeat)
Thursday 9.30 PM People Channel **Friday 10.30 PM** Kairali
Saturday 8 PM Kairali (Repeat) **5.30 PM** People Channel (Repeat)

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